

IMPROVING THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF MULTI-STOREY MONOLITHIC RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS MADE OF REINFORCED CONCRETE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6473108>

prof. **Sayfiddinov Sadriddin, Shermamatov Jasur – Master (TIAC)**

Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Obstruction: *The article presents ways to improve the energy efficiency of multi-storey reinforced concrete monolithic residential buildings.*

Keywords: *get-up-and-go redemptional in the production, interpretation and cognitive operation of introductory construction materials. Energy-saving agglutinative geomaterials. contemporary morphologic and heat-insulating construction substances.*

Introduction The main reduction in heat consumption for heating buildings is carried out by increasing the heat-shielding properties of building envelopes. These include residential and public buildings with periodic heating - country cottages, household buildings, shift workers, etc.

Thermal protection of buildings” presents modern regulatory requirements for thermal protection, including the fulfillment of sanitary and hygienic and comfortable conditions, as well as the condition for energy saving. The above regulatory document contains a list of buildings and structures to which the energy saving condition does not apply. The thermal regime of such buildings is non-stationary due to the frequency of operation of the heating system and changes in the temperature of the internal air during their operation. Due to the high demand for the construction of individual housing in suburban and rural areas, energy efficiency issues in such buildings are currently very relevant. The specific characteristic of thermal energy consumption for heating and ventilation of a building is a value that characterizes the energy efficiency class of a building. This value is determined at the design stage by calculation based on architectural solutions, climatic conditions of the construction area, the composition of the enclosing structures, the frequency of air exchange, the choice of a heating system, and the use of highly efficient energy-saving technologies. In this regard, when designing buildings for individual residential development, it is necessary to take into account all the above factors and carefully approach the choice of design solutions, as well as engineering life support systems. In residential buildings of individual development, the main costs of thermal

energy are spent on compensating for heat losses through fences. For houses operated in the standby heating mode, along with the coefficient of heat transfer through the fences, it is necessary to take into account dynamic indicators characterizing the speed of heating of the premises. To be able to heat up the premises, it is necessary to use fast-heating, low-heat-intensive heating devices that respond to changes in the temperature of the coolant in a short period of time. As a rule, in suburban areas, in addition to residential buildings, there are heated baths, garages and various outbuildings (a schematic is shown in Figure 1). With a large number of heated buildings, it is advisable to design a separate source of thermal energy to satisfy the need for thermal energy of the above complex of buildings. With such a heat supply scheme, it is necessary to install heat routes from the heat source to consumers by air or underground laying methods. To reduce heat losses from pipelines of heating networks, it is necessary to choose highly efficient thermal insulation of pipelines, which also allows, in case of emergency, to increase the cooling time of the coolant in the pipes. A competent choice of enclosing structures, a heat supply system, elements of a heating system can reduce energy costs for heating buildings and ultimately increase the energy efficiency of the residential complex in question. When designing buildings with intermittent heating due to variable thermal conditions, it is necessary to take into account the dynamic characteristics of heating systems and building envelopes. Currently, there is no engineering methodology for assessing the energy efficiency of buildings operated in conditions of intermittent heating. also allowing in emergency situations to increase the cooling time of the coolant in the pipes. A competent choice of enclosing structures, a heat supply system, elements of a heating system can reduce energy costs for heating buildings and ultimately increase the energy efficiency of the residential complex in question. When designing buildings with intermittent heating due to variable thermal conditions, it is necessary to take into account the dynamic characteristics of heating systems and building envelopes. Currently, there is no engineering methodology for assessing the energy efficiency of buildings operated in conditions of intermittent heating. also allowing in emergency situations to increase the cooling time of the coolant in the pipes. A competent choice of enclosing structures, a heat supply system, elements of a heating system can reduce energy costs for heating buildings and ultimately increase the energy efficiency of the residential complex in question. When designing buildings with intermittent heating due to variable thermal conditions, it is necessary to take into account the dynamic characteristics of heating systems and

building envelopes. Currently, there is no engineering methodology for assessing the energy efficiency of buildings operated in conditions of intermittent heating. elements of the heating system can reduce energy consumption for heating buildings and ultimately increase the energy efficiency of the considered residential complex. When designing buildings with intermittent heating due to variable thermal conditions, it is necessary to take into account the dynamic characteristics of heating systems and building envelopes. Currently, there is no engineering methodology for assessing the energy efficiency of buildings operated in conditions of intermittent heating. elements of the heating system can reduce energy consumption for heating buildings and ultimately increase the energy efficiency of the considered residential complex. When designing buildings with intermittent heating due to variable thermal conditions, it is necessary to take into account the dynamic characteristics of heating systems and building envelopes. Currently, there is no engineering methodology for assessing the energy efficiency of buildings operated in conditions of intermittent heating.

The degree of development of the research topic A great contribution to solving the problems of improving the energy efficiency of buildings and structures was made by research by peoples and foreign scientists published in monographs and scientific articles, the study of which made it possible to formulate the tasks of the dissertation work.

Many issues related to the energy efficiency of buildings and structures are considered in the works of Russian scientists B.A. Semenov, V.N. Bogoslovsky, E.G. Malyavina, D.Yu. Petrova, E.Yu. Anisimova, V.I. Panferova, T.A. Datsyuk, Yu.P. Ivleva, V.A. Pukhkala, V.G. Gagarina, Yu.A. Tabunshchikova, Yu.S. Vytchikova, A.G. Kocheva, N.A. Tsvetkova, A.I. Eremkina, A.M. Beregovoy, A.M. Grititlina, T.V. Schukina. The research of these scientists indicates great promise in the field of intermittent heating. However, due to insufficient knowledge of this topic and the lack of methods for thermal engineering calculation of enclosing structures and elements of the heating system under conditions of variable thermal conditions, further study of this problem is necessary, which makes the research topic relevant.

Research objectives:

- mathematical modeling of thermal processes in the enclosing structures of buildings and structures operated under conditions of variable thermal conditions;

- development of an engineering methodology for calculating the dynamic characteristics of heating devices;
- development of an engineering methodology for calculating the dynamic characteristics of building fences;
- experimental studies of the dynamic characteristics of heating devices;
- development of highly efficient thermal insulation of pipelines of the heat supply system;
- optimization of design solutions for building envelopes with intermittent heating.
- feasibility study for the use of intermittent heating for buildings and structures.

The object of the research is the enclosing structures, elements of the heating and heat supply system of buildings of individual development, operated in conditions of intermittent heating. The subject of the study is the dynamic characteristics of building envelopes and elements of heating systems, heat-shielding characteristics of external walls and energy consumption for the operation of buildings with intermittent heating.

Scientific novelty of the obtained results:

- analytical dependencies were obtained to determine the energy consumption and heating time of multilayer fences, as well as a mathematical dependence to calculate the maximum allowable value of the thickness of the heat-insulating material of the outer fence of a building operating in conditions of a variable thermal regime;
- a mathematical model was developed and mathematical dependences were obtained to determine the energy consumption and heating time of enclosing structures with screen thermal insulation, an analytical relationship was established between energy consumption and the thickness of the air gap;
- on the basis of solving a non-stationary heat transfer problem, a formula was obtained for finding the heating time of heating devices, and an assessment of the heating time of radiators made of various materials was carried out based on the results of theoretical and experimental research;
- a new design protected by a patent for thermal insulation of pipelines of heat supply systems based on polyurethane foam shells is proposed.

The theoretical and practical value of the work lies in the fact that, on the basis of a theoretical study, a method for determining the heating time and energy consumption of multilayer fences of buildings operated under conditions of a variable thermal load is proposed. Wall structures have been developed that have minimal energy consumption for their heating. A

technique for assessing the energy efficiency of buildings operated under conditions of a variable thermal regime is proposed. Based on the analysis of theoretical and experimental studies, the values of the exit time of various heating devices to the stationary mode of operation were obtained. For pipelines of the heat supply system of buildings and structures, a model of highly efficient thermal insulation has been developed, and a patent for a utility model has been obtained.

Research methodology and methods: methods of mathematical physics and the theory of heat and mass transfer, experimental and theoretical methods for studying engineering systems and building envelopes. The reliability of the obtained research results is ensured by the use of modern methods of engineering calculations, as well as verified laboratory equipment. All studies and calculations were performed in accordance with regulatory documentation and state standards.

Conclusion. The main component of the heating system are heaters. Currently, there are a large number of different heating devices on the market. In the process of heating the room, a change in the thermal power of the heating devices occurs, as a result of which the air temperature in the room changes.

REFERENCES:

1. Grimitlin, A.M. Energy Efficiency: Interferences and Successes [Text] / A.M. Grimitlin // Plumbing, heating, air conditioning. - 2015. - No. 7. - S. 86-87.
2. Datsyuk, T.A. Modeling of the thermal regime of residential premises with intermittent heating [Text] / T.A. Datsyuk, Yu.P. Ivlev, V.A. Pukhkal // Modern problems of science and education. - Moscow, 2014. - No. 5. - S. 69-70.
3. Datsyuk, T.A. Modeling the microclimate of residential premises [Text] / T.A. Datsyuk, V.R. Taurit // Bulletin of Civil Engineers. -SPb., 2012. - No. 4. - P.196-198.
4. Datsyuk, T.A. The results of modeling the microclimate of residential premises with various types of heating devices [Text] / T.A.
5. Datsyuk, Yu.P. Ivlev, V.A. Pukhkal // Civil Engineering Journal. -2013. - No. 6. - P.12-21. Datsyuk, T.A. Assessment of energy efficiency indicators of buildings [Text] / T.A. Datsyuk, A.M. Grimitlin, E.A. Anshukova // Bulletin of civil engineers. - 2018. - No. 5. - P.141-145.